

Salmonella control programme according to Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003: Results for 2009

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The EU-wide *salmonella* control programme provides for all Member States to submit an annual report on the percentage of *salmonella*-positive flocks of breeding poultry (*Gallus gallus*), laying hens and broilers. To meet this requirement, all *Länder* (German federal states) submit their data to the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) which then evaluates the data.

The data reported for 2009 show that the established Community targets for breeding poultry (1%) and broilers (1%) were either maintained or reached. In official sampling, *salmonella* serovars targeted in the control programmes were found in 0.8% of breeding poultry and in 0.4% of broilers. In laying hens, the detection rate for *salmonella* serovars targeted in the control programmes was 4.8%, which was higher than in the previous year.

Changes in detection rates are also possibly the result of improved reporting. This supports the relevance of harmonised reporting for the consistent implementation and assessment of control programmes.

If only the results from official testing are taken into account, the detection rate of the five *salmonella* serovars targeted in the control programmes in breeding poultry were below the Community target established for *salmonella* control and thus complied with the target, as they have in previous years. If, however, test results reported by food business operators are also taken into account the result appears differently. Under these circumstances, the *salmonella* findings in laying hens clearly exceeded the Community target. Compared with the relatively low detection rates of the previous year, *salmonella* detection was not reduced further.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on
http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/salmonellen_bekaempfungsprogramm_gemaess_verordnung_eg_nr_2160_2003_ergebnisse_fuer_2009.pdf